

SUPER PV PROJECT – INNOVATIVE AND HIGH-QUALITY PV SYSTEMS TO REGAIN LEADERSHIP OF EUROPEAN PV BUSINESSES ON THE WORLD MARKET

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ABSTRACT: PV deployment growth is an unmatched success story in the energy sector over recent years. However, European PV manufacturers are facing a decline in production due to competition from third countries. The fragmentation of the value chain is believed to be one of the major factors for this decrease in the competitiveness. SUPER PV is a collaborative European-funded project initiated in 2018 by 26 partners in reaction to this trend. It pursues a significant LCOE reduction for innovative PV systems based on a hybrid combination of technological innovations and data management solutions along the PV value chain. Responding to the need of evaluating proposed innovations in terms of economic feasibility and market trends, a dedicated task force, an Exploitation Team, was introduced at the beginning of the project as a main instrument for overseeing achievement of KPI's and beyond, in the ever-changing landscape of the PV sector.

Keywords: Solar PV, LCOE, Economic Analysis, PV Market, LCA

1 INTRODUCTION

PV deployment growth is an unmatched success story in the energy sector over recent years. In just 12 years the world's cumulative solar capacity increased by over 7,600% - from merely 6.6 GW in 2006 to 505 GW by the end of 2018 [1]. Today PV is in an ever-increasing share of regions becoming the cheapest unsubsidised form of electricity, with emerging business models based primarily on levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) estimations. To succeed in this very competitive PV market European, PV manufacturers are facing the need for innovations addressing not only technology but also business models based on data management solutions, understanding that without such hybrid approach they can completely disappear from the market.

SUPER PV is a collaborative European-funded project initiated in 2018 by 26 organizations in reaction to this trend. In the SUPER PV project, we are proposing a combined solution addressing both product technological quality and business operation, targeting a **significant reduction of LCOE**. This reduction will be achieved through demonstration of a careful selection of innovations, which will improve the main components of the LCOE (CAPEX, OPEX and PR¹). Introducing **SUPERior** quality PV systems will create conditions for accelerating large scale deployment of PV in Europe for both utility (non-urban) and residential scenarios and help EU PV businesses to regain leadership and competitiveness on the global market.

2 PROJECT SCOPE AND APPROACH

2.1 Scope

To achieve ground-breaking impact on cost reduction, **the project concept is tackling in integral way the following three cornerstone value chain steps impacting PV system LCOE: module, power electronics (PE) and system integration/OPEX.**

-- PV module innovations: Cost reduction on the PV module level can be achieved by three main factors: i) increase the PV module efficiency/yield with moderate/no additional production costs, ii) reduce the material cost by using less or cheaper materials, iii) increase the service lifetime by producing more reliable PV modules. The first factor (efficiency/yield increase) also reduces costs on system level due to less BoS (Balance of System) costs per installed kWp with higher efficiency/yield. The second factor (material savings) reduces the production costs of the PV module. The third factor (increase reliability) is often difficult to address in cost calculations since typical assumed PV service lifetimes are equal or higher than typical financial life models for PV systems. However, we address the lifetime by choosing bifacial PV modules, which have due to its rigid structure an expected service lifetime of at least 30 years as main development basis for our innovations. Furthermore, the bifacial PV modules allow to gain 5%-25% more energy yield for the same installed capacity by additionally collecting diffuse light from the rear [2] [3].

Within the PV modules innovations, we address all three reduction factors. We increase the efficiency/yield of the PV module by improving the optical and thermal properties of the modules. The introduction of multi-

¹ CAPEX – capital expenditure, OPEX – operational expenses, PR – performance ratio.

functional nanoparticle-based coatings will act as anti-reflection, anti-soiling and infra-red reflection, aiming for enhanced yield including reduced module temperature, and reduced module cleaning costs. Furthermore, we address material cost savings for the module production by substituting and recycling expensive materials. The manufacturers SOLITEK, APOLLON and FLISOM will transfer the successful innovations on module level to test production. The successful transferred innovations will be tested on field demonstration sites and the cost efficiency will be assessed to reach the final goal of LCOE cost reduction. The demo sites will be operative from 2020 and onwards in altogether 7 locations in Europe and North Africa: Tozeur – Tunisia, Ourzazate & Rabat – Morocco, Sevilla – Spain, Vilnius – Lithuania, and Oslo & Trondheim – Norway.

-- **Power Electronics development:** innovations for PE are focusing on module level power electronics (MLPE) and are forming an integral solution ensuring significantly higher power output on the system level by ability to ensure performance monitoring and data collection on single module string level and long-term stability of operation, independently of geographical and operational conditions. Proposed hardware level innovations are also ensuring efficient utilization of innovations targeted at OPEX cost reduction.

-- **PV system integration and process innovation:** Nowadays, PV installers dealing with PV manufacturing, invest significant amount of resources (with an impact on the final electricity cost from PV) to convert potential clients requests for a PV plant into a project proposal with a technical layout, economic offer (efficiency-performance / cost threshold) and feasibility analysis for production/installation. This process could be significantly optimized through data management solutions. To increase the process quality reducing costs, an optimized **digital process** based on the **information management** would reduce efforts, time, repetitive work, risk of mistakes, information losses, etc., transforming an almost “manual” and **fragmented** work into a digitized and interoperable workflow along all the value chain. The challenges to future large-scale deployment of PV could be overcome by a new methodology that we call **PIM (Photovoltaic information modelling/management)**: a digital and holistic process, supported by innovative digital tools, methodologies and platforms, ensuring clear structures, efficient processes, less time, lower costs and higher quality across the entire PV plant lifecycle.

Starting from this approach, the digitalization that we introduce in this project is expected to be replicable for the whole value chain of solar PV, to be tailored from raw material to electricity, including also building applied and integrated-PV.

2.2 Overall Project Approach

Project overall methodology is based on three phases approach:

-- **Development of technology innovations and novel data management tools** up to prototype level.

-- **Testing of the innovations and methods in real conditions.** Testing will be performed in three different climatic regions of extreme conditions: i) tropical equatorial climate, ii) hot desert climate and iii) cold climate.

-- **Evaluation of the effectiveness of the proposed solutions.** For the SUPER PV systems state of the art module production technologies available for industrial

partners were selected to provide possibility for comparable analysis of different technologies and their prospects for cost reduction.

3 AMBITION FOR SUPER PV CUMULATIVE LCOE REDUCTION

The SUPER PV project aims to demonstrate an innovative PV system cost reduction and consequently significant **LCOE [4] (Levelized Cost of Electricity) reduction of 26-37%** by adopting a hybrid approach, combining technological innovations and Data Management methods along the PV value chain.

As the solar module costs have decreased significantly in recent years, BoS costs have become a critical factor in determining lifecycle costs (LCOE) and the total installation costs.

Figure 1 is presenting cumulative picture of targeted by SUPER PV cost reduction expressed by LCOE relative to reference products reduction for each of value chain steps addressed by the project (PV module, PE and system integration).

Figure 1: SUPER PV Project ambition for LCOE reduction (irradiation 1320 kWh/m²/yr)

Taking into account predictions for PV system cost reduction according to various sources [5] [6] [7] [8], by the planned end of the project in 2022, SUPER PV systems will be superior product on the worldwide market according to Figure 2.

Figure 2: Project related PV systems LCOE projections compared to market predictions.

4 ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY OF RESULTS

4.1 Introduction

The stated ambition in **LCOE reduction refers to the identified state-of-the-art situation** as described in the SUPER PV proposal, submitted in September 2017, and from which **benchmark values** have been established.

Nonetheless, **monitoring the technology and market evolution of the PV sector** will be an important task within the project, not just from a market competition perspective, but also from a technology development point-of-view as SUPER PV will not cover the entire supply chain needed to produce PV electricity at the lowest possible cost.

In order to ensure such monitoring of technology and market evolution along the project development, and assess the economic viability of project innovations and fine-tune the exploitation strategy of SUPER PV, key functions were introduced from the beginning of the project:

--An appointed **Exploitation Team**; composed of the main partners dealing with project coordination, exploitation and dissemination. The Exploitation Team oversees Technology and market watch, Business case modelling, Replication plan, Risk assessment and Freedom to Operate analysis. The Exploitation Team reports to the project's **Exploitation Board**, that includes one representative of each partner, meeting in connection with each SUPER PV Project Meeting with the main role of identifying the exploitation potential of the project's results and to build proposed exploitation scenarios.

4.2 Defined Key Performance Indicators (KPI's)

Techno-economic and environmental assessment of SUPER PV results are based on the following defined KPI's:

- KPI 1: Solar module cost reduction
- KPI 2: BoS components costs (EUR/Wp)
- KPI 3: Total installation cost (EUR/Wp)
- KPI 4: Performance Ratio (PR) over the lifetime
- KPI 5: Reduction of lifecycle costs per kWh, expressed by the LCOE
- KPI 6: Recyclability and environmental footprint of solar modules

Reaching the defined KPI's is essential for the success of SUPER PV. The rationale for applying the above parameters is as follows:

-- **KPI 1-3 [Solar module cost reduction, BoS component costs, total installation costs]:** The module cost and BoS components costs (€/Wp) are technology dependent and also subject to the global marketplace, while system installation costs adding up to the final LCOE are more specific to location and segment. Thus, module and BoS components costs will tell whether a technology developed in SUPER PV is competitive at a European level. The LCOE metric on the other hand will tell whether SUPER PV is a viable energy source in different regions of Europe, and it falls naturally both for cost and for risk assessment that the LCOE will be evaluated at various conditions reflecting local specificities in different regions.

-- **KPI 4 [Performance Ratio (PR) over the lifetime]:** The Performance Ratio is the quotient of alternating current (AC) yield and the nominal yield of the generator's direct current (DC), and it is a globally accepted indicator to judge the performance of grid connected PV Plants. PR is affected by the solar module's operating temperature, inverter's conversion efficiency, soiling (dust, snow),

shading, wiring losses and electrical mismatch between solar cells in a module (and between modules in an inverter string).

-- **KPI 5 [Reduction of lifecycle costs per kWh, expressed by the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE)]:**

The LCOE is one of the solar industry's most commonly used metrics and it is also widely used to compare lifetime performance of different electricity generating technologies.

-- **KPI 6 [Recyclability and environmental footprint of solar modules]:** The methodology applied to perform this assessment follows the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). Life Cycle perspective approach will be adopted to assess this technology and, specifically, LCA methodology will be applied, following ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 to assess the environmental impacts associated with the PV systems throughout their lifecycle. Special attention will be paid to resources consumption and materials recovery. For this reason, the recycling of the PV systems will be analysed in detail in order to evaluate the potential environmental reductions.

4.3 Benchmark values for KPI's from the SUPER PV proposal

As stated before, SUPER PV ambition is established based on the identified state-of-the-art situation as described in the project proposal.

-- **KPI 1-3 [Solar module cost reduction, BoS component costs, total installation costs]:** A review of statistics and forecasts [9][10][11] indicated at the time of proposal submission (Sept 2017) that the state of the art system installation cost was about 1 EUR/Wp for utility scale solar PV and 1.27 EUR/Wp for rooftop solar PV, respectively, and module prices were at 0.45 EUR/Wp. This gives us a cost distribution as given in Table I.

Table I: Solar PV installation cost distribution, as stated in the SUPER PV proposal

	Utility scale		Rooftop	
	EUR/Wp	share	EUR/Wp	share
Solar module cost	0.45	45 %	0.45	35 %
Inverter & balance of system	0.55	55 %	0.82	65 %
System installation cost	1.0		1.27	

In the period since Sept 2017, module and installation costs have been reduced significantly. Implications of this are discussed in Ch. 5.

-- **KPI 4 [Performance Ratio (PR) over the lifetime]:** Reviews of PR development [12][13][14] show that values have evolved from 50% to 75% in the 1980s, via 70–80% in the 1990s, to >80% today, with some systems close to 90%.

-- **KPI 5 [Reduction of lifecycle costs per kWh, expressed by the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE)]:** Many factors influence the LCOE, and it might not be possible to come up with a global estimate or target. Some non-technological factors with a potential large influence on the LCOE that may vary from project to project, are: Solar insolation; system capacity as well as site location and configuration, themselves influencing various factors such as economies of scale, installation cost or operation & maintenance costs; domestic regulation; cost of capital; maturity and effectiveness of the local PV market. Reported LCOE ranges are wide also due to methodological discrepancies between different sources.

Moreover, Power Purchase Agreement (PPA) prices are not equal to LCOE, as the LCOE represents current conditions prevailing in the industry, while the PPA is a promised price for a future project, and it should come as no surprise that recent competitive PPA bids are markedly lower than reported LCOE for existing facilities. Nevertheless, the successful bidder winning a PPA must deliver solar electricity at the agreed PPA price, and to be profitable, the PPA price for a given project cannot be lower than its LCOE.

Some statistics and estimates for unsubsidized solar PV are given in Table II.

Table II: LCOE overview, unsubsidized utility scale solar PV, SUPER PV proposal (2017) and updated (2019)

Source	US ct/kWh		Comments
	2017	2019	
Lazard [15][16]	6.2	4.0	Low end. Mc-Si, single-axis tracking, 50 MW system, US South West, 60 % debt at 8 % interest rate and cost of equity at 12 %.
ITRPV [1][9]	3.7	3.2	2000 kWh/kWp
	4.9	4.3	1500 kWh/kWp
	7.3	6.5	1000 kWh/kWp
IRENA [17][18]	13 (2015)	8.5 (2018)	Global weighted average utility-scale solar PV.
Various sources	< 3	< 2	PPA's UAE, Chile, Mexico (2016-17) PPA's Brazil, Portugal (2019) High insolation, low capital cost

-- **KPI 6 [Recyclability and environmental footprint of solar modules]:** The key metrics assessing this KPI are:

- ✓ *Carbon Footprint of solar modules*; expressed in kg of CO₂ equivalent per kWh produced by the module over the lifetime. The indicator evaluates the life cycle emissions due to the production, installation, use-phase and end of life management of the solar modules, including the materials and balance of plant used.
- ✓ *Primary Energy demand of solar modules*; expressed in MJ. This indicator evaluates the life cycle energy consumption as primary energy from both renewable and non-renewable sources due to the production, installation, use-phase and end of life management of the solar modules. From this metric *the energy payback time* for SUPER PV modules operating under different conditions can be assessed.
- ✓ *Ratio of recycled material*. This metric will be evaluated considering the amount of materials coming from the installed solar system that can be recycled at the end of life to produce secondary materials.

5 PRELIMINARY ASSESSMENT OF MAIN RESULTS

At this point in the project it is still early to reassess the performance of SUPER PV innovations with respect to the defined KPI's in Ch. 4.2, as the demonstration sites spread over Europe and North Africa will not be operative

before 2020.

What we however can observe is that the price reduction in parts of the PV supply chain not covered by SUPER PV, is something we can take advantage of, and already we can see that SUPER PV technologies, in combination with relevant technologies and practices outside the scope of the SUPER PV project, may form winning combinations on the market, driving costs and LCOE further down compared to our benchmark (Ch. 3). Taking BoS as an example – recent cost reductions in this part of the PV supply chain will alone contribute to a further reduced LCOE in the order of 8-10 % compared to the original SUPER PV benchmark in Ch. 3 (utility scale solar PV in Europe).

6 SUMMARY and CONCLUSIONS

The SUPER PV project approach with focus on monitoring of PV market development and constant adjustment of project research and innovation activities in line with market situation is similar to commercial companies' strategies for new products entrance into the market. Companies are very careful about adoption of new technologies and innovations and without careful estimation of new technology impact on CAPEX and OPEX will not invest into new products uptake. SUPER PV as cooperative project has several advantages comparing to internal commercial RTD activities: first of all project business partners have possibility to combine several innovations coming from renowned research centres into single technological solution with cumulative impact on product costs and efficiency, secondly integrating RTDI activities along value chain they are gaining mutual benefits from developments in other steps of the value chain, and last but not least cooperative project is reducing RTDI costs per single manufacturer by shared research and mutual learning. It is still long and challenging way to full scale impact of the SUPER PV project, but our project team is confident that adopted approach for project results uptake will give EU PV manufacturing businesses competitive advantage on the global PV market.

7 REFERENCES

- [1] International Technology Roadmap for Photovoltaic Results, 2018
- [2] B. V. Aken, L. Okel, J. Liu, S. Luxembourg and J. v. Roosmalen, White Bifacial Modules – Improved STC Performance Combined with Bifacial Energy Yield, 32nd EUPVSEC, pp. 42 - 47, 2016.
- [3] U. A. Yusufoglu, T. M. Pletzer, L. J. Koduvelikulathu, C. Comparotto, R. Kopecek and H. Kurz, Analysis of the Annual Performance of Bifacial, IEEE JPV, vol. 5, pp. 320-328, 2015.
- [4] A. Velosa & M. Aboudi, in SolarServer, 2010, Ch. 03-11-2010.
- [5] IRENA, The Power to Change: Solar and Wind Cost Reduction Potential to 2025, 2016
- [6] GTM Research, Nov. 2016 <https://www.greentechmedia.com/articles/read/report-how-much-does-a-solar-pv-system-cost-in-2016>
- [7] EU JRC PV status report, Oct. 2016 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/310800467_PV_Status_Report_2016

- [8] ISE Fraunhofer, Jan. 2017
<https://www.ise.fraunhofer.de/content/dam/ise/en/documents/publications/studies/recent-facts-aboutphotovoltaics-in-germany.pdf>
- [9] International Technology Roadmap for Photovoltaic Results, 2016
- [10] GTM Research, Nov. 2016, [PV system cost 2016](#)
- [11] EU JRC PV status report, Oct. 2016, DOI: 10.2790/682995
- [12] W. Sark et al., Review of PV performance ratio development, 2012, DOI: 10.13140/2.1.2138.7204
- [13] A. Woyte et al., Monitoring of Photovoltaic Systems: Good Practices and Systematic Analysis, EUPVSEC, 2013.
- [14] A.M. Khalid et al., Performance ratio – Crucial parameter for grid connected PV plants, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.07.066>
- [15] <https://www.lazard.com/media/438038/levelized-cost-of-energy-v100.pdf>
- [16] <https://www.lazard.com/perspective/levelized-cost-of-energy-and-levelized-cost-of-storage-2018/>
- [17] IRENA, REthinking Energy, 2017
- [18] <https://www.irena.org/publications/2019/May/Renewable-power-generation-costs-in-2018>